

and residency of the remaining 20% are unknown. Nonresident owners were probably land speculators holding rather than developing the land; 4 of the 9 nonresident owners in the township owned land in 2 sections of sections 4-9. From 1839-1849, nonresidents owned the land comprising the main site of the LTER in section 4. In 1850 the site was bought by John Finley, who resided on site until 1869. By 1873, he had sold this property to F.W. Ford, also a resident. Ford in turn sold the land to J.K. Flower in 1910, who kept it until 1928.

It seems likely that the LTER main site was not tilled until 1850 when Mr. Finley purchased and resided on the land. He is known to have been a 'progressive agriculturalist' who grew cereals. In 1850 Kalamazoo county had 62,000 ha in farmland. Farmland area in the county peaked at 134,000 ha in 1910. At present farmland is 62,000 ha. The number of farms in the county had similarly peaked in 1910: there were 1,100 farms in 1850, 3,372 farms in 1910, and 745 farms today. In Ross Township there were 2,200 ha in farmland in 1850, 8,700 ha in farmland in 1899, and 8,000 ha in farmland in 1959. Township farms numbered 40 in 1850, 183 in 1897, and for the final year of information, 1934, there were 120 farms.

Kalamazoo County row crops from 1850-1953 included primarily wheat, corn, and oats in rank order. Potatoes, buckwheat, and rye were also common. From 1954 to the present, corn has dominated, with soybeans next most common. Oats disappeared as the use of draft animals dwindled post-WWII. Wheat has gradually declined in importance. County forage lands were dominated by grasses from 1878-1920s, after which legumes became more prominent; most forages today are legumes. Cropping patterns in Ross Township show a similar trend for the 100 years of information available.

Suggested citation: Tomecek, M.B. and G.P. Robertson. 1996. Land Use History for the Kellogg Biological Station and the Surrounding Area. Kellogg Biological Station Long-term Ecological Research Special Publication. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2579176>.

Acknowledgments

Support for this research was provided by the National Science Foundation Long-term Ecological Research Program (DEB 92-11771) at the Kellogg Biological Station and by the Michigan Agricultural Experiment Station.

See also:

Burbank, D. H., K. S. Pregitzer, and K. L. Gross. 1992. Vegetation of the W.K. Kellogg Biological Station. Michigan State University Agricultural Experiment Station Research Report 510, East Lansing, Michigan, USA.

Gray, S. E. 1996. The Yankee West: community life on the Michigan frontier. The University of North Carolina Press, Chapel Hill, North Carolina, USA.

Michigan Natural Features Inventory. 2019. Vegetation circa 1800. MSU Extension, Michigan State University. <https://mnfi.anr.msu.edu/resources/vegetation-circa-1800> . (For Kalamazoo County, see <https://mnfi.anr.msu.edu/data/veg1800/kalamazoo.pdf>; for Barry County, see <https://mnfi.anr.msu.edu/data/veg1800/barry.pdf>).